

Valorisation of seawater desalination brine via cultivation of a halotolerant microalga in bubble column photobioreactors

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HIGHLIGHTS

- *P. parvum* grows efficiently in 100 % brine, reaching 1.9 g L^{-1} biomass in 17 days.
- Salinity drives the increase of SFAs + MUFAs from 70 % to 83 % of total fatty acids.
- Carotenoids increase by ~25 % under brine-induced oxidative stress.
- Fractions from *P. parvum* reveal selective cytotoxic and antimicrobial activities.
- Brine valorisation supports sustainable microalgal biorefineries and circular economy.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the valorisation of seawater desalination brine (61 g L^{-1}) by cultivating the halotolerant microalga *Prymnesium parvum* in 10-L bubble column photobioreactors, previously acclimated to a broad salinity range ($5\text{--}61 \text{ g L}^{-1}$). Under optimized nutrients and irradiance, brine-based cultures achieved biomass yields (1.9 g L^{-1}) comparable to seawater controls. Salinity altered biomass composition, increasing saturated and mono-unsaturated fatty acids (up to 83 % of total fatty acids) and reducing polyunsaturates, suggesting membrane remodelling. Carotenoid content increased by 25 % under salinity-induced stress. Methanolic extracts and solvent fractions showed strong bioactivity. CH₂Cl₂ and BuOH fractions inhibited >85 % of cancer cell growth across lines; several fractions also exhibited antimicrobial and antiphytopathogenic effects. These findings highlight *P. parvum*'s potential for integrated brine management while generating valuable microalgal biomass, reducing freshwater use and supporting circular bioeconomy. However, further research is needed to assess limitations and validate techno-economic feasibility at larger scale.

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1. Introduction

Desalination is becoming an increasingly viable fresh water supply option, offering the potential to provide an unlimited and climate-independent source of high-quality water. However, seawater desalination plants generate vast amounts of high-salinity brine, posing considerable environmental risks due to both its salinity and the presence of additional substances such as nitrates and phosphates, altering the chemical and physical characteristics of receiving waters, and negatively impacting marine ecosystems, ultimately threatening biodiversity (Gilani et al., 2024). Accordingly, the International Desalination Association advocates for the development of advanced strategies for brine management (Yildirim et al., 2022). Among the proposed approaches, microalgae-based desalination brine treatments represent a promising, sustainable, and cost-effective solution. These systems may not only mitigate brine discharge but also generate valuable biomass for various applications, contributing to a green circular bioeconomy. However, research in this area remains limited, mostly restricted to laboratory-scale studies and focused on brines with significantly lower salinity than seawater — typically derived from brackish groundwater desalination in inland regions (Gilani et al., 2024). The few existing studies involving seawater desalination brine have exclusively focused on *Dunaliella salina* for carotenoid production (Ortega Méndez et al., 2012), revealing a critical gap in current knowledge regarding broader applications. However, this strategy can leverage not only inherently halophilic microalgae like *Dunaliella*, but also halotolerant species (Ishika et al., 2019; Shetty et al., 2019). Generally, microalgae accumulate lipids and high-value products, such as carotenoids, under salt stress. However, gene expression profiles vary significantly depending on whether the microalga is salt-sensitive, salt-adapted, or naturally salt-tolerant (Shetty et al., 2019).

The halotolerant haptophyte *Prymnesium parvum* is one of the main ichthyotoxic species involved in harmful algal blooms. Due to its high plasticity, this cosmopolitan species thrives across freshwater, brackish, and marine ecosystems (Anestis et al., 2021). *P. parvum* is a potential biodiesel feedstock (Hemaiswarya et al., 2012). Nevertheless, the economic viability of microalgae-based biorefineries requires co-production of high-value metabolites with applications in sectors such as pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and nutraceuticals (Park et al., 2022). *P. parvum* synthesises several noteworthy polyketide secondary metabolites, including prymnesins, which exhibit antifungal, antibacterial, and antineoplastic properties (Dembitsky, 2022). As a representative of the haptophytes, *P. parvum* also generates significant amounts of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as EPA (eicosapentaenoic acid), and DHA (docosahexaenoic acid) (Nedbalová et al., 2016) and carotenoids, such as fucoxanthin (Zapata et al., 2004). Although previous studies have reported that salinity significantly affects fatty acid production in *P. parvum* (Nedbalová et al., 2016), its effect on carotenoid synthesis remains unexplored. Although the species is recognised for its biotechnological potential (Richardson and Patiño, 2021), there is no available evidence describing the cultivation of *P. parvum* in photobioreactors using seawater desalination brine as a culture medium. Nor is there any information about its biochemical potential under such hypersaline conditions, despite the thorough investigation of other species (Bartley et al., 2013; Ishika et al., 2019; Yildirim et al., 2022). This represents a significant knowledge gap regarding the potential applications of *P. parvum*.

This study aims to address this gap. It was divided in two parts. First, laboratory-scale flask cultures were used to gradually acclimate *P. parvum* to different salinities to assess the effects of salinity on growth, biomass productivity, and photosynthetic performance. Second, cultures were scaled up in bubble column photobioreactors (BC-PBRs) to evaluate continuous growth in media formulated with seawater desalination brine. The biomass harvested from the BC-PBRs was then analysed for fatty acid and carotenoid content. Methanolic extracts were also subjected to solvent partitioning to assess their anticancer, antimicrobial,

and antiphytopathogenic activity. This study provides a preliminary evaluation of the feasibility of using *P. parvum* to valorise seawater desalination brine through a microalgae-based biorefinery approach.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The microalga

The marine microalga *Prymnesium parvum* BMCC283, provided by the Basque Microalgae Culture Collection (Spain), was used. The inoculum was prepared as described elsewhere (López-Rosales et al., 2025). Briefly, cells were cultured in 50 mL Erlenmeyer flasks at 18 ± 1 °C under a 12/12 h light–dark cycle. The lighting system consisted of light emission diode (LED) strips attached to a rectangular-shaped flat reflective plastic cover. The flasks were illuminated from above. The mean PAR irradiance on the flask culture surface was 300 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, measured with a QSL-100 quantum scalar irradiance sensor (Biospherical Instruments, San Diego, USA). The f/2 medium formulation (Guillard, 1975) modified to have a molar N/P ratio of 5 by increasing the P concentration up to 181 μM , prepared with filter-sterilised ($22 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$ filter, Millipore Corp., Billerica, MA, USA) Mediterranean seawater (38 g salt L^{-1}) was used both to maintain the inoculum and as the basis for the experiments.

2.2. Seawater and brine

The culture experiments were conducted using Mediterranean seawater and brine obtained from a reverse osmosis (RO) desalination plant. Seawater was collected from the coastal area near the desalination facility, while the brine was kindly supplied by the municipal desalination plant in Almería, Spain (Latitude 36.81639°N, Longitude: -2.42431°O , population 200,753 inhabitants). This plant processes approximately 70,000 m^3 of seawater per day and generates an average of 35,000 $\text{m}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$ of brine as a by-product. For seawater analysis, three samples collected on different days were used. A total of twelve parameters were analysed: total dissolved solids (TDS) by gravimetry; Cl^- , Na^+ , SO_4^{2-} , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Br^- , NO_2^- , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , and F^- by HPLC. These components are considered major ions in both seawater and brine. The results of the intake water and brine analysis were provided by the municipal desalination plant of Almería, managed by the company Acciona Agua S. A. The seawater composition was as follows (mg L^{-1}): TDS, 38,000; Cl^- , 20,673; Na^+ , 11,661; SO_4^{2-} , 2,976; Mg^{2+} , 1,394; Ca^{2+} , 440; K^+ , 428; Br^- , 75.6; NO_2^- , 0.4; NO_3^- , 0.2; PO_4^{3-} , < LOQ; and F^- , 0.3. The intake water composition was as follows (mg L^{-1}): TDS, 32,000; Cl^- , 17,067; Na^+ , 9,195; SO_4^{2-} , 2,116; Mg^{2+} , 1,154; Ca^{2+} , 462; K^+ , 240; Br^- , n. a.; NO_2^- , n. a.; NO_3^- , 4; PO_4^{3-} , < LOQ; and F^- , 1.6. The brine composition was as follows (mg L^{-1}): TDS, 61,000; Cl^- , 35,007; Na^+ , 18,390; SO_4^{2-} , 4,848; Mg^{2+} , 2,229; Ca^{2+} , 987; K^+ , 480; Br^- , n. a.; NO_2^- , n. a.; NO_3^- , 6.9; PO_4^{3-} , < LOQ; and F^- , 3.2. Interestingly, several ion concentrations in the feedwater to the plant were found to be lower than those in open seawater, except for calcium, potassium, fluoride and especially nitrate, which was nearly 20 times higher. This discrepancy is likely due to the water source: the plant draws from beach wells. Additionally, the facility is located in an area with significant intensive greenhouse agriculture, which may have contributed to elevated nitrate levels in the local aquifer.

2.3. Bench-scale culture experiments

The influence of salinity on the growth of *P. parvum* was assessed in controlled bench-scale batch cultures. Experiments were carried out in 100 mL Erlenmeyer flasks containing 50 mL of culture medium. The flasks were shaken by an orbital shaker (3-cm of shaking diameter) at agitation speed of 100 rpm. No evidence of cell damage due to hydrodynamic stress was observed. All experiments were conducted under the conditions described in section 2.1. The initial pH was adjusted at 8.5

using 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. The initial biomass concentration was of $10.7 \pm 5.8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. A total of twelve culture media were prepared. The media were categorised based on their salt concentrations relative to natural seawater (38 g L^{-1}) and was used as the control condition (coded as CTRL). Brackish media with salinity below 38 g L^{-1} were prepared by diluting seawater with distilled water, resulting in salinity levels ranging from 0 (100 % distilled water) to 30 g L^{-1} . These cultures were coded as S0 to S30. Hypersaline media were prepared by mixing brine with a salt concentration of 61 g L^{-1} with natural seawater (38 g L^{-1}) in different proportions, yielding salinity levels ranging from 45 g L^{-1} to 61 g L^{-1} . These experiments were coded as S45, S50, S55, and BRINE. Each experiment was carried out in duplicate.

To ensure that observed responses reflected true physiological adaptation rather than transient stress, all cultures were inoculated with *P. parvum* cells acclimated to each specific salinity level. Thus, a three-step acclimation process was implemented. For each salinity level, three sequential 14-day batch subcultures were performed, resulting in a total cultivation time of 42 days per condition and 72 batch cultures in total. At the end of each subculture, cells in the early stationary phase were used to inoculate the subsequent batch. This approach ensured that long-term acclimation mechanisms were fully established before data analysis. *P. parvum* demonstrated the ability to grow under all the tested salinity conditions except in the medium without any added marine salt (S0, 0 g L^{-1}), where no growth was observed across the three sequential subcultures. Previous studies have reported that microalgae typically require at least one full cultivation cycle to acclimate to new environmental conditions before consistent growth can be established (López-Rosales et al., 2025). The extended acclimation period allowed sufficient time for *P. parvum* to activate its adaptive mechanisms and maintain growth under most salinity regimes without compromising photosynthetic performance. Consequently, only the results from the final subculture for each salinity condition were considered in the analysis and discussion, as they most accurately represent the stable, acclimated response of *P. parvum* to each salinity level.

2.4. Culture in bubble-column photobioreactors

A proof-of-concept study evaluated the feasibility of cultivating *P. parvum* in hypersaline media using BC-PBRs. Based on the results obtained in the flask experiments, three culture media were selected for upscaling: (i) CTRL-PBR, using natural seawater (38 g L^{-1} salt); (ii) BRINE-PBR, using 100 % reject brine from the desalination plant (61 g L^{-1} salt); and (iii) S50-PBR, prepared by mixing approximately equal parts of natural seawater and brine to reach a final salinity of 50 g L^{-1} , consistent with the CTRL, BRINE, and S50 cultures in the flask experiments, respectively.

The characteristics and operational procedures of the BC-PBRs were adapted from previous work (López-Rosales et al., 2025). Briefly, the BC-PBRs consisted of 10-L vertical bubble columns made of poly(methyl methacrylate) with a 9 cm internal diameter and a 175 cm height. Aeration was provided at a rate of 1 L min^{-1} (i.e., 0.1 vvm) through a 2-mm nozzle sparger, delivering filtered ambient air. Illumination was supplied by RGBWW LED strips mimicking the sunlight spectra (Edison Opto Co., Taiwan) wound around the BCs to provide an uniform irradiance distribution in the photobioreactor. The culture temperature was maintained at $20 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and the pH was automatically regulated at 8.5 by injecting carbon dioxide as needed.

The experimental strategy implemented in CTRL-PBR, BRINE-PBR, and S50-PBR is detailed in Table 1. The approach aimed to dynamically improve biomass production by carefully varying the key culture parameters. These included the concentration of the $f/2$ medium nutrients (either $f/2 \times 3$ or $f/2 \times 6$), light/dark (L/D) photoperiod (12:12, 18:6 and 24:0), and irradiance level (I_0) during the light phase (600 or $1,000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). These variables were combined within a sequential batch cultivation scheme comprising four successive subcultures (sets 1 to 5), as outlined in Table 1. Each experiment was

Table 1

The strategy used in the pilot-scale bubble column photobioreactors (BC-PBRs) for the growth of *P. parvum* under three salinity conditions: 100 % seawater (CTRL-PBR), 50 % seawater +50 % brine (S50-PBR), and 100 % brine (BRINE-PBR). Five experimental sets were defined in terms of irradiance level (I_0), light/dark (L/D) cycle, daily mean irradiance (Y_0) received by the culture and initial concentration of nutrients.

Set	Interval (d)	I_0 ($\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	L/D cycle (h)	Y_0 ($\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	Nutrients
1	0–18	600	12:12	300	$f/2 \times 3$ (N:P = 5)
2	18–35	600	18:6	450	$f/2 \times 3$ (N:P = 5)
3	35–48	600	24:0	600	$f/2 \times 6$ (N:P = 5)
4	48–63	1,000	24:0	1,000	–
5	63–80	1,000	24:0	1,000	$f/2 \times 6$ (N:P = 5)

initiated with a primary batch culture (set 1) consisting of 9 L of the selected culture medium and 1 L of inoculum. The inoculum was obtained from bench-scale cultures that had been previously acclimated to the specific salinity conditions of each experiment. Upon reaching the stationary growth phase, a defined volume of culture was withdrawn and replaced with fresh medium to initiate the next subculture in sets 2, 3 and 5). For these sets, the replenished fresh medium was supplemented with phosphate and nitrate stock solutions to adjust the final concentrations of these nutrients in the entire culture volume (10 L) according to the values specified for each set. The remaining nutrients were added in quantities matching the original composition of the respective culture medium (refer to Table 1). In set 4, neither culture volume was withdrawn nor additional nutrients were added; only the incident light intensity was increased to determine whether light limitation was constraining biomass production. To analyse biomass and supernatants, harvested culture samples were processed by centrifugation using a batch centrifuge (Beckman Coulter, model Allegra 25R, Madrid, Spain) at $6,000 \times g$ for 5 min to separate cell pellets from the liquid phase.

Although closed PBRs generally exhibit low evaporative losses (Guieysse et al., 2013), water loss due to evaporation was monitored and compensated throughout the 80-day cultivation period. Distilled water was added to each BC-PBR at the end of each set (days 18, 35, 48, 63, and 80 in Table 1), based on the visible volume markings on the columns. Since losses were regularly corrected, no significant bias was introduced into biomass concentration values. Additionally, sample volumes taken for biomass measurements were immediately replaced with base culture medium of the corresponding salinity, ensuring constant working volume throughout the experiment.

2.5. Analytical measurements

The biomass concentration on a dry weight basis (C_b) in the culture was determined in triplicate from samples taken throughout the culture by measuring the absorbance at 720 nm ($C_b \text{ (g L}^{-1}) = 0.9 \times \text{OD}_{720}$; $r^2 = 0.9$, $n = 39$). The maximum photochemical yield of photosystem II (F_v/F_m) was used as an indicator of microalgae cell stress. F_v/F_m was measured using a pulse amplitude modulation (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometer (Mini-PAM-2500; Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich, Germany). All the analysis were performed in duplicate. The total nitrate and phosphate in the supernatants were measured using the 4,500-N and 4,500-P spectrophotometric methods. The fatty acids were quantified by gas chromatography. The carotenoid content was analysed using an HPLC system equipped with a diode-array detector, following a protocol and extraction conditions previously proposed (López-Rosales et al., 2025) optimized for *P. parvum*. Briefly, 5 mg of lyophilized biomass were extracted in darkness using 1 mL of a ternary solvent mixture consisting of ethanol (76 % v/v), hexane (18 % v/v), and water (6 % v/v). After 2 min of vortexing, the samples were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 2 min

at room temperature. The supernatants were filtered through a $22 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m}$ filter prior to HPLC analysis. HPLC calibration was performed using standards for fucoxanthin, β -carotene, diadinoxanthin, and diatoxanthin (DHI, Hørsholm, Denmark).

2.6. Bioactivity assays

Dry methanolic crude extracts obtained from lyophilized biomass harvested from the CTRL-PBR and BRINE-PBR cultures were fractionated using a sequential solvent-partitioning process based on polarity, as described elsewhere (López-Rodríguez et al., 2021). This process yielded five polarity-based fractions: hexane (Hex), carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4), dichloromethane (DCM), *n*-butanol (BuOH) and water (H_2O). The antiproliferative potential was tested against a panel of four human cancer cell lines: A549 (lung carcinoma), HT-29 (colon adenocarcinoma), MDA-MB-231 (breast adenocarcinoma), and PSN-1 (pancreatic

adenocarcinoma), all sourced from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, Manassas, VA, USA). The bioassays were conducted following the methodology described elsewhere (Schleissner et al., 2017), and results were reported as the percentage of growth inhibition for each cell line: 100 % means that all cells were lysed (strong cytotoxic effect); 0 % means that there were as many cells as the control. No cytotoxicity was observed from any of the solvent-derived dry extracts tested.

Antiphytopathogenic and antimicrobial activities were evaluated at Medina Foundation (Granada, Spain, <https://www.medinadiscovery.com>) using in-house plant and human pathogenic strains, as well as strains from the ATCC collection, following established protocols (Audoín et al., 2013; Martínez et al., 2019). The phytopathogenic panel included six agricultural fungi (*Colletotrichum acutatum*, *Verticillium dahliae*, *Fusarium proliferatum*, *Fusarium cubense* TR4, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Magnaporthe grisea*) and one bacterial species (*Clavibacter michiganensis*

Fig. 1. Growth of *Prymnesium parvum* in bench-scale flask cultures and pilot-scale bubble column photobioreactor (BC-PBR) cultures. (a) Effect of salinity on specific growth rate during the exponential growth phase (μ_m), and maximum photochemical quantum yield of photosystem II (F_v/F_m) in bench-scale flask cultures; the control condition corresponding to natural seawater (38 g L^{-1}) is coded as CTRL; the remaining media are coded as S_i based on their salt concentration, as defined by i , and BRINE with a salt concentration of 61 g L^{-1} . (b) Final biomass concentration (C_{bm}) and biomass productivity (P_{bm}) in bench-scale flask cultures. (c) Temporal dynamics of biomass concentration (C_b) in cultures grown in pilot-scale BC-PBR under different salinities: 100 % seawater (CTRL-PBR), 50 % seawater +50 % brine (S50-PBR), and 100 % brine (BRINE-PBR). The cultivation strategy involved sequential subcultures (sets 1 to 5) with progressively increasing nutrient concentrations and irradiance levels. Values in (a), (b), and (c) represent means \pm standard deviation (SD) from duplicate acclimated cultures at each salinity level. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) determined by one-way ANOVA are indicated by different lowercase letters.

CECT790). For antimicrobial bioassays, one fungal strain (*Candida albicans*) and four human pathogenic bacterial strains were tested: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* PAO-1, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, methicillin-sensitive *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA) ATCC 29213, and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) MB5393. Bioactivities were assessed after 24–48 h, with measurements performed in duplicate and results reported as mean values.

2.7. Statistical analysis

One-way ANOVA was performed to determine differences between treatments, using Statgraphics Centurion 19.2.02 (StatPoint, Herndon, VA, USA). Statistically significant differences in the mean response among the treatments were fixed at 5.0 % significance level threshold (p value < 0.05). The method used to discriminate between the means at the 95.0 % confidence level was Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) procedure.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Influence of salinity on the growth of *P. Parvum*

To compare the performance of *P. parvum* acclimated to different salinity levels in flask cultures, the following kinetic parameters were used: the specific growth rate during the exponential growth phase (μ_m), the final biomass concentration (C_{bm}), and the biomass productivity at the end of the culture (P_{bm}). The F_v/F_m ratio was used as an indicator of potential salinity-related stress in the cells. Fig. 1a shows the values of μ_m and F_v/F_m , while Fig. 1b presents C_{bm} and P_{bm} , all corresponding to the third batch culture of the bench-scale experiments. One-way ANOVA confirmed that salinity level significantly influenced μ_m , C_{bm} , and P_{bm} ($p < 0.05$). As expected, since the original *P. parvum* strain was isolated from a marine environment, the highest μ_m ($18 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; $p < 0.05$) was observed in the CTRL culture (natural seawater, 38 g L⁻¹ salt). Growth rate was inhibited at both low and high salinity levels, indicating that cells grew sub-optimally when cultured outside their preferred salinity range. Nevertheless, *P. parvum* maintained consistent growth in both hyposaline (S5 to S30) and hypersaline (S45 to BRINE) conditions. For instance, cultures at the lowest tested salinity (S5) reached a μ_m of $13 \times 10^{-2} \pm 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (a 28 % decrease relative to CTRL culture; $p < 0.05$), and those at the highest salinity (BRINE, 61 g L⁻¹) reached $11 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (a 39 % decrease relative to CTRL; $p < 0.05$). The ability of the cells to adjust their metabolism and survive at both low and high salt concentrations was evident. This capacity for acclimation under changing salinity conditions is a well-documented trait among microalgae (Hellebust, 1985). In particular, *P. parvum* possesses genes related to osmoregulation, salinity stress response, ion transport and acetate metabolism, which support its adaptability to saline environments, even though growth is affected under extreme salt concentrations (Talarski et al., 2016). Evidence also indicates that *P. parvum* can adapt to long-term growth in environments with varying salinity and ion compositions (Richardson and Patiño, 2021).

The F_v/F_m ratio is a widely accepted proxy for overall cell status in microalgae. Under hyposaline conditions (S5 to S30), F_v/F_m remained stable, with an average value of $63 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2 \times 10^{-2}$ (Fig. 1a), indicating optimal physiological performance and absence of significant stress (Masojídek et al., 2010). In hypersaline conditions (S45 and S50), values remained also above 0.6, except in the BRINE culture, where a slight decline to $57 \times 10^{-2} \pm 2 \times 10^{-2}$ ($p < 0.05$) was observed, suggesting the onset of mild stress. These findings corroborate early observations indicating that elevated salinity reduces photosynthetic activity in microalgae, thereby limiting the energy and carbon available for growth (McLachlan, 1961). Similarly, a relationship has been observed between reduced photosynthesis rates and lower growth rates under saline stress (Hart et al., 1991).

The trends in C_{bm} and P_{bm} displayed in Fig. 1b closely followed those observed for μ_m (Fig. 1a). The highest C_{bm} ($270 \pm 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and P_{bm} ($17.2 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$) were achieved in the CTRL culture, while the BRINE culture exhibited reductions of approximately 48 % and 53 % ($p < 0.05$), respectively. Similar declines were noted at the lowest salinity levels. Under salinity stress, *P. parvum* likely reallocates metabolic energy toward maintaining osmotic balance rather than biomass accumulation (Ishika et al., 2018; Kirst, 1990). Despite this, the species demonstrated the capacity to acclimate and sustain growth across a broad salinity range. These findings highlight the robust salinity tolerance of *P. parvum*, supporting its potential use in hypersaline environments such as those associated with desalination brine reuse.

3.2. Potential of hypersaline photobioreactor cultures: Pilot-scale experiments

The promising outcomes obtained with BRINE cultures at bench-scale warranted further evaluation under larger-scale to assess the feasibility of sustained, high-yield biomass and by-products production. Such scale-up is essential for preliminarily assessing commercial potential, as it must demonstrate not only productivity and operational stability but also environmental sustainability (Moheimani, 2013). In particular, minimizing the use of freshwater (a limited natural resource) is a critical consideration in the development of viable algal bioprocesses (Ishika et al., 2018; Ishika et al., 2019). In this context, the reuse of brine from seawater desalination plants as a culture medium for salinity-acclimated microalgae is a promising strategy. This approach may enhance the synthesis of valuable metabolites, increase process flexibility and cost effectiveness. Importantly, it also aligns with environmental sustainability goals by providing a near-closed-loop solution for mitigating the environmental footprint associated with brine disposal (Tambat et al., 2025).

A conceptual framework for integrating seawater desalination with microalgal cultivation is illustrated in Fig. 2a. In low-salinity systems, freshwater and seawater can be blended in varying proportions to compensate for evaporative losses and maintain target salinity levels, thereby reducing the freshwater consumption. A variant of this strategy has recently been applied in “agro-to-agro” circular bioprocesses, where seawater desalination brine was used to adjust the salinity of hydroponic wastewater for cultivating marine microalgae to produce a bio-based agricultural fungicide (López-Rosales et al., 2025). Conversely, in hypersaline microalgal cultures (i.e., those with salinities exceeding that of seawater), evaporative losses and salinity adjustments can be managed entirely with mixtures of seawater and brine, thereby eliminating the need for freshwater inputs. Provided the selected microalgal species exhibits sufficient halotolerance, such as *P. parvum*, the complete substitution of freshwater becomes feasible. Furthermore, in closed PBRs, evaporative losses are minimal compared to open systems, further enhancing water-use efficiency. To validate the scalability and long-term reproducibility of the bench-scale results, representative hypersaline conditions (S50 and BRINE) were selected for pilot-scale cultivation using bubble column photobioreactors (BC-PBRs). Culture media were prepared as described in section 2.4. Operational strategies for each BC-PBR setup are detailed in section 2.4 and summarized in Table 1.

3.2.1. Growth dynamics

Culture profiles for the cultures in the BC-PBRs are displayed in Fig. 1c. Inocula for the set 1 cultures were derived from flask cultures previously acclimated to their respective salinity levels. Transitions between sets (see Table 1) were implemented when cultures reached the stationary phase or exhibited prolonged linear growth, indicating either exhaustion of essential nutrients or growth limitation due to suboptimal supply rates of key resources such as light and/or CO₂, respectively. Progressive improvements in growth and biomass yield were observed across all conditions as growth-limiting factors, namely nutrient concentration ($f/2$ medium) and irradiance (Y_0), were systematically

Fig. 2. Conceptual diagram illustrating the integration of a seawater desalination plant with a microalgal photobioreactor system and a simplified model of *Prymnesium parvum*'s response to salinity increase. (a) Diagram showing the proposed circular bioeconomy framework, in which seawater and brine are used to formulate microalgal culture media, minimizing freshwater demand. Salinity is adjusted through controlled mixing of desalination streams. S1 and S2 represent flow splitting while M represents flow mixing. (b) Salinity-induced ROS boosts lipid and carotenoid production, enhancing membrane stability and photosystem protection — key traits for biorefinery targeting of high-value compounds (based in part on prior studies).

addressed. F_v/F_m remained stable throughout the cultivation period, with overall average value of $63 \times 10^{-2} \pm 3 \times 10^{-2}$, indicative of healthy, non-stressed cells throughout the culture period (Ishika et al., 2018).

In set 1, all three cultures were initiated with a biomass concentration of 50 mg L^{-1} . However, a noticeable adaptation phase was observed, particularly in the BRINE-PBR culture. To minimize this lag phase in set 2, the initial biomass concentration was increased to 100 mg L^{-1} . This was achieved by reducing the withdrawn culture volume from each reactor, based on the C_{bm} reached in set 1. Specifically, 8 L were withdrawn from the CTRL-PBR, 7.5 from the S50-PBR, and 7 L from the BRINE-PBR. This increase in inoculum biomass, combined with higher irradiance, resulted in improved C_{bm} across all conditions ($p < 0.05$). In set 3, the initial biomass concentration was further increased to 400 mg L^{-1} to accelerate culture establishment and reduce the lag phase even more. To achieve this, the withdrawn volumes were adjusted according to the C_{bm} reached in set 2: 4.3 L for CTRL-PBR, 3.8 L for S50-PBR, and 3.3 L for BRINE-PBR. In addition to the higher inoculum concentration, both nutrient levels and irradiance were increased in set 3 (see Table 1). Despite the improved starting conditions and nutrient enrichment, biomass accumulation plateaued prematurely. This was unexpected, as the culture received double the nutrient concentration compared to set 2, suggesting that nutrient limitation was unlikely to be the main

constraint. The early onset of the stationary phase instead pointed to light limitation under the given operating conditions.

Consequently, in set 4, nutrient concentrations were kept unchanged, and only the irradiance level was further increased ($Y_0 = 1,000 \text{ } \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). This adjustment led to a marked improvement in biomass yields, particularly in CTRL-PBR and S50-PBR. Although the improvement in BRINE-PBR was less pronounced ($p < 0.05$), the overall increase in biomass production in set 4 supports the hypothesis that light, rather than nutrient availability, was the limiting factor in set 3. To further investigate this, nitrate and phosphate concentrations were monitored at the end of sets 2–5 to assess potential nutrient limitation. The results showed that both nutrients were completely exhausted at the end of sets 2, 4, and 5, whereas remained at relatively high residual concentrations at the end of set 3, averaging $3,676 \pm 212 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$ for nitrate and $804 \pm 41 \text{ } \mu\text{M}$ for phosphate across the three PBRs. These results indicate that nutrient depletion was not responsible for the onset of the stationary phase in set 3. Instead, the resumption of growth upon increasing irradiance in set 4, without any nutrient addition, strongly supports the conclusion that light limitation was the predominant factor constraining biomass accumulation.

Under the conditions of set 5, which replicated those of set 4, the cultures were inoculated at the same biomass concentration used in set 3 (400 mg L^{-1}). To achieve this, 8 L were withdrawn from the CTRL-PBR

and the S50-PBR cultures, and 7.5 L from the BRINE-PBR. The cultures exhibited similar growth dynamics to those observed in set 4, confirming full physiological acclimation. In set 5, CTRL-PBR achieved values of C_{bm} ($1,980 \pm 40 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and P_{bm} ($105 \pm 3 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$), representing a 3.5-

fold increase compared to set 1 ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, BRINE-PBR attained a C_{bm} of $1,870 \pm 100 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ and a P_{bm} of $98 \pm 4 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$, nearly six times greater than in set 1 ($p < 0.05$), and approximately 13-fold higher than in BRINE flask culture ($p < 0.05$). These substantial

Fig. 3. Fatty acid profile of *Prymnesium parvum* biomass grown in pilot-scale bubble column photobioreactors (BC-PBRs) under three salinity conditions at the end of set 5: 100 % seawater (CTRL-PBR), 50 % seawater + 50 % brine (S50-PBR), and 100 % brine (BRINE-PBR). Values in (a) to (o) represent means \pm standard deviation (SD) from duplicate acclimated cultures at each salinity level. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) determined by one-way ANOVA are indicated by different lowercase letters.

increases are attributable not only to higher nutrient concentrations and irradiance, but also to continuous CO₂ supply via aeration and improved mass transfer efficient in the BC-PBRs. Interestingly, unlike flask experiments (Fig. 1a, b), in the BC-PBRs *P. parvum* exhibited similar growth in hypersaline media (BRINE-PBR and S50-PBR) as in natural seawater (CTRL-PBR) (Fig. 1c, set 5), underscoring the suboptimal nature of flask conditions with respect to CO₂ supply, nutrient availability, mixing, mass transfer, and light exposure.

These findings demonstrate the successful scale-up of *P. parvum* cultivation under hypersaline conditions using a semi-continuous cultivation strategy in pneumatically agitated PBRs. The gradual increase in light intensity and nutrient availability facilitated physiological acclimation and prevented photo-inhibition, ensuring robust biomass production. Moreover, cultivation in seawater desalination brine aligns with circular economy goals by drastically reducing freshwater inputs (thereby achieving a near-zero water footprint) through the reuse of a saline industrial byproduct. Hypersaline conditions not only extend the cultivation period of salt-tolerant microalgae (Ishika et al., 2018), but also confer ecological advantages, such as reducing the risk of contamination by non-target organisms (Bartley et al., 2013) and promoting the synthesis of high-value metabolites (Tambat et al., 2025). This is the case for *P. parvum*. While semi-continuous cultivation improved the growth of *P. parvum* and resulted in comparable C_{bm} across the three salinities tested, the high-salinity environment affected the accumulation of key metabolites, such as fatty acids and carotenoids, as discussed in the following sections.

3.2.2. Fatty acids

Fig. 3 presents the relative content of saponifiable fatty acids (FAs) in the dry biomass at the end of set 5. The identified FAs included saturated fatty acids (SFAs) such as myristic acid (14:0), palmitic acid (16:0), and stearic acid (18:0); monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) such as palmitoleic acid (16:1n7), oleic acid (18:1n9), and eicosenoic acid (20:1n9); and long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) such as stearidonic acid (18:4n3), arachidonic acid (20:4n6), eicosapentaenoic acid (20:5n3), docosapentaenoic acid (22:5n3), and docosahexaenoic acid (22:6n3). This FAs profile is consistent with that previously reported for a brackish strain of *P. parvum* (Nedbalová et al., 2016). As shown in Fig. 3, salinity influenced the FA content ($p < 0.05$). Total FAs increased with salinity from $78 \pm 1 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ d.w. in CTRL-PBR to $86.9 \pm 1.1 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$ d.w. in BRINE-PBR (Fig. 3D), representing an 11.4 % increase ($p < 0.05$). Salinity also altered the degree of FA unsaturation and the proportion of FAs. In general, higher salinity promoted the accumulation of SFAs (Fig. 3m) and MUFAs (Fig. 3n), while reducing PUFA content (Fig. 3o). Since final biomass concentrations did not differ significantly among the three salinity conditions (Fig. 1c, set 5), the observed changes in FA content translate directly into proportional changes in overall FA yields.

Studies in microalgae suggest that lipids serve as high-energy carbon reservoirs to facilitate cellular adaptation to stressful environmental conditions (Ishika et al., 2018). Increased salinity promotes reactive oxygen species (ROS) accumulation, which shifts carbon flux towards the oxidative pentose phosphate pathway to generate NADPH for ROS detoxification. While glycolysis may persist to meet energy demands, this metabolic reprogramming prioritizes redox balance, leading to a buildup of intracellular reducing equivalents. To mitigate redox imbalance and maintain cellular homeostasis, excess reducing power is redirected into lipid biosynthesis, a mechanism demonstrated in microalgae under salt stress (Shi et al., 2020). Moreover, cell membrane remodelling under diverse environmental stressors involves not only alterations in the lipid content but also modifications in the fatty acid moieties (Goss and Latowski, 2020).

In this sense, as shown in Fig. 3, the increase in salinity, especially in the BRINE-PBR culture, showed the most pronounced redistribution of FAs, with significant increases in SFAs and MUFAs, and a notable reduction in PUFAs. Similar shifts have been reported for *P. parvum* (Nedbalová et al., 2016) and are well documented in many other algal

species under salt stress (for a comprehensive review of the salt stress effect in the FA profile and saturation/unsaturation in microalgae, see Cañavate and Fernández-Díaz, 2022). PUFAs are essential constituents of polar lipids (e.g., glycolipids and phospholipids) that form the structural matrix of biological membranes. Their presence influences critical physical membrane properties, such as bilayer thickness, permeability, and fluidity, all of which are vital for maintaining membrane function under oxidative stress conditions, such as those induced by high salinity (Harayama and Riezman, 2018). PUFAs synthesis is typically upregulated under optimal growth conditions, presumably driven by the heightened demand for membrane biogenesis associated with active cellular proliferation (Huang et al., 2020). However, under stress conditions, increased ROS diffusion across membranes promotes PUFAs partitioning and favours the accumulation of SFAs, many of which may result from the hydrolytic breakdown of plastid membrane lipids (Maciel et al., 2024). This trend is evident in the marked decrease in the (MUFAs + PUFAs)/SFAs ratio (an indicator of the membrane fluidity), which fell from 0.7 in the CTRL-PBR to 0.6 in the S50-PBR and then to 0.5 in the BRINE-PBR. This clearly shows a decrease in fluidity and permeability, which protects the plasma membrane from injury (Kan et al., 2012). Although changes in membrane fluidity are widely recognized as key triggers of cellular acclimation processes, the molecular mechanisms underlying the sensing and transducing of these signals through biological membranes remain largely hypothetical and poorly understood.

3.2.3. Carotenoids

In addition to triggering lipid accumulation, excessive ROS also exert cytotoxic effects by oxidatively damaging vital macromolecules, including proteins, membrane lipids, and DNA. To counteract this oxidative burden, microalgae induce the overproduction of carotenoids, which act as efficient ROS scavengers and play a central role in maintaining redox homeostasis under stressful conditions (Shi et al., 2020). Fig. 4a shows the relative content of carotenoids in the dry biomass at the end of set 5. Although the carotenoids content differed significantly among the three cultures, all samples contained fucoxanthin (Fx), diadinoxanthin (Ddx), diatoxanthin (Dtx), and β -carotene (β -car). Salinity clearly influenced total carotenoid content, with an increase observed as salinity increased ($p < 0.05$). Total carotenoid content ranged from ~0.8 % to 1 % d.w. for the CTRL and BRINE cultures respectively, with fucoxanthin being the predominant carotenoid, ranging from 0.4 % to 0.5 % d.w. This carotenoids profile is consistent with that reported for *P. parvum* in previous studies (Berger et al., 1977; Laviale and Neveux, 2011). Because the final biomass concentrations were statistically similar across the three salinity conditions (Fig. 1c, set 5), the observed increases in carotenoid content are expected to translate into equivalent increases in total carotenoid yield.

As can be seen from Fig. 4a, the results clearly show that all four carotenoids are involved in protecting the cells against the action of ROS, since the concentration of all of them, except Dtx, increases with increasing salinity. Carotenoids are predominantly localized within pigment-protein complexes embedded in the thylakoid membrane, where they fulfil essential structural and photofunctional roles within the photosynthetic apparatus. They contribute to the stabilization of membrane architecture and facilitate the dissipation of excess energy. The core complexes of photosystem I (PSI) and photosystem II (PSII) are particularly enriched in β -car, a key carotenoid involved in photo-protection and energy transfer. Similarly, the presence of Fx, Ddx, and Dtx in the light-harvesting complexes (LHCI and LHCI) underscores the multifaceted role of carotenoids in light capture and energy dissipation (Maciel et al., 2024).

Notably, Ddx and Dtx are not solely confined to protein-bound states; they are also found as free pigments distributed across the thylakoid and chloroplast envelope membranes (Bojko et al., 2019). These free xanthophylls participate in the xanthophyll cycle specific to diatoms, dinophytes, and haptophytes commonly referred to as the Ddx cycle,

Fig. 4. Carotenoid composition and bioactivities profiles of *Prymnesium parvum* grown in pilot scale bubble column photobioreactors (BC-PBRs). (a) Total and individual carotenoid (fucoxanthin, diadinoxanthin, diatoxanthin, and β-carotene) contents expressed as % of dry weight of *P. parvum* grown in BC-PBRs under three salinity conditions at the end of set 5: 100 % seawater (CTRL-PBR), 50 % seawater + 50 % brine (S50-PBR), and 100 % brine (BRINE-PBR). Values represent means ± standard deviation (SD) from duplicate acclimated cultures at each salinity level. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) determined by one-way ANOVA are indicated by different lowercase letters. (b) Bioactivities profiles of *P. parvum* extracts obtained from biomass produced in CTRL-PBR and BRINE-PBR cultures. The scheme on the left shows the solvent-partitioning process of biomass crude extract into five fractions of increasing polarity. The right panel summarizes anti-proliferative activity, antimicrobial, and anti-phytopathogenic activities across the crude extract and fractions.

which constitutes a sophisticated strategy engaged in antioxidant defence of microalgal cells. This cycle occurs within the lipid phase of the thylakoid membrane and is inherently dependent on the biophysical properties and molecular composition of the membrane lipids (Goss and Latowski, 2020). Given that the Ddx cycle involves the enzymatic and non-enzymatic interconversion of Ddx, a light harvesting pigment, to Dtx, a photoprotective pigment, in response to excess ROS generated by high salinity, the data in Fig. 4a show that in the CTRL-PBR and S50-PBR experiments the de-epoxidation of Ddx to Dtx was similar, but was highly increased in the BRINE-PBR experiment, with a marked decrease in Ddx and a concurrent increase in Dtx concentrations. Significantly, the pool (Ddx + Dtx) was the same in the three experiments ($2.3 \pm 0.1 \text{ mg g}^{-1} \text{ d.w.}$). This suggests that this xanthophyll cycle contributed significantly to cells acclimation to salinity stress in the BRINE-PBR experiment since Dtx is an effective quencher of ROS and facilitates the energy dissipation in the photosynthetic apparatus, promoting the integrity of antenna complexes, photosystems, and membranes (Bojko et al., 2019; Ramanna et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2018). Thus, cell growth in the culture with the highest salinity (BRINE-PBR) was supported to a comparable extent as in the culture maintained at optimal salinity levels (CTRL-PBR).

Moreover, the accumulation of Dtx in BRINE-PBR is closely associated with a reduction in membrane fluidity, likely mediated by the FAs redistribution, increased lipid ordering, and restricted molecular diffusion within the hydrophobic core. This biophysical adjustment may act as a protective mechanism, stabilizing membrane structures against oxidative damage or structural perturbation (Goss and Latowski, 2020). Taken together, these findings highlight the critical role of the xanthophyll cycle (particularly the conversion of Ddx to Dtx) in enhancing halotolerance in *P. parvum*. By coupling membrane lipid remodelling with dynamic carotenoid metabolism, the cells are able to maintain photosynthetic performance and membrane integrity under high salinity, as outlined in Fig. 2b. These mechanisms are not exclusive to *P. parvum*; they likely operate in other halophilic or halotolerant microalgae equipped with an active xanthophyll cycle (Bojko et al., 2019). This suggests a broader adaptive advantage among marine microalgae, enabling them to thrive in hypersaline environments through a finely tuned intricate interplay of structural and biochemical stress responses related to membrane lipid composition, carotenoid metabolism and oxidative stress.

3.2.4. Bioactivity of *Prymnesium parvum* extracts

Bioactivity assessments performed on methanolic crude extracts from *Prymnesium parvum* and their solvent-partitioned fractions were determined as described in section 2.6. Given the absence of systematic differences between extracts derived from CTRL-PBR and BRINE-PBR cultures across the various bioactivities, results presented in Fig. 4b represent the averaged data from both conditions. There were selective biological activities across antiproliferative, antiphytopathogenic, and antimicrobial assays.

In antiproliferative assays, extract fractions presented marked antiproliferative effects on cancer cell lines, particularly in the CH_2Cl_2 and BuOH fractions with percentages of growth inhibition exceeding 85 % in all cell lines. The CCl_4 fraction also displayed strong activity against breast adenocarcinoma and pancreas adenocarcinoma cells, while the hexane and aqueous fractions had moderate effects. This bioactivity profile indicates that potentially cytotoxic compounds are more prevalent in mid- to low-polarity extracts. It is improbable that the observed activity is due to prymnesins, as these compounds are most effectively extracted and dissolved in polar organic solvents, rather than in water or non-polar solvents (Manning and La Claire, 2010). Nevertheless, their potential contribution in moderately polar organic fractions such as BuOH cannot be completely excluded. Comparative analysis with a previous study on *Chrysochromulina rotalis*, cultivated in seawater using a tubular photobioreactor, reinforces the key role of solvent polarity in shaping cytotoxic activity (Macías-de la Rosa et al., 2023). Despite the

differences in cultivation systems and media used, the antiproliferative effects were strongest in the fractions obtained with moderately polar solvents, such as dichloromethane, from both species. However, notable differences emerged: while the hexane and BuOH fractions of *C. rotalis* were minimally or not active, the corresponding fractions in *P. parvum* displayed moderate to strong activity, suggesting the presence of additional or differently distributed lipophilic bioactives. Interestingly, when hexane was substituted by cyclohexane in *C. rotalis*, the resulting fraction exhibited moderate activity, indicating that slight differences in non-polar solvent properties can influence the recovery of cytotoxic compounds (Macías-de la Rosa et al., 2023). These observations highlight that, although polarity-driven extraction remains a reliable strategy to enrich cytotoxic compounds in marine haptophytes, species-specific metabolic outputs and solvent-specific solubility profiles can significantly influence which fractions yield the most bioactive potential.

The results of the antimicrobial tests against human pathogens showed selective inhibition. The most apolar fractions were excluded. The BuOH and DCM fractions exhibited unequal activities against *Candida albicans*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), but none against *Acinetobacter baumannii* and methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* (MRSA). The lack of activity against MRSA, despite moderate sensitivity in MSSA, underscores the specificity of the active compounds and their potential limitations or targets. These observations align with a bioactivity pattern often attributed to structurally complex, moderately polar secondary metabolites. Antiphytopathogenic tests were not carried out with the most apolar fractions (hexane and carbon tetrachloride) because due to their limited relevance in agricultural applications (apolar compounds often exhibit poor solubility in aqueous media and reduced bioavailability, making them less suitable for the development of biopesticides). Results revealed that the mid- to high-polarity fractions (DCM, BuOH) exhibited inhibitory activity against the bacterium *Clavibacter michiganensis* as well as the majority of the economically relevant fungal pathogens tested, except *P. syringe* and *P. carotum*. Levels of activity depended on the polarity of the fraction and the pathogen.

The differential activity profiles across fractions suggest a polarity-dependent distribution of active compounds. Fractions such as DCM may concentrate oxidized lipids or semipolar pigments, while BuOH, known to retain amphipathic molecules, may include glycosylated lipids or prymnesins — highly bioactive polyether toxins previously associated with *P. parvum*. Although not detected directly in this study, the polar character and broad-spectrum activity of the BuOH fraction are consistent with the presence of such metabolites. Additionally, the aqueous fraction may contain smaller polar compounds, such as peptides or phenolic derivatives, contributing to selective antimicrobial effects. The above discussion does not rule out the involvement of unknown metabolites in the observed bioactivities. Future work will focus on dereliction to identify both known and novel compounds. The latter will require isolation and NMR-based structural elucidation.

Based on available evidence, this work provides the first integrated report of antiproliferative, antifungal, and antibacterial activities associated with *Prymnesium parvum* biomass extracts. The results broaden the known bioactivity landscape of this species, previously studied mainly for its ichthyotoxicity, and underscore its untapped potential in applications ranging from crop protection to antimicrobial drug discovery. Interestingly, no direct relationship was observed between the detected bioactivities and the observed salt-stress-induced modulation of fatty acids and carotenoids, suggesting that unknown active compounds likely arise from distinct biosynthetic pathways. Further metabolomic profiling and bioassay-guided fractionation will be essential to identify the active compounds and potentially uncover novel bioactives with potential applications. In summary, *P. parvum* exhibits selective and multi-targeted bioactivities that support its consideration as a promising microalgal source in biorefinery schemes aimed at producing high-value compounds for agricultural and pharmaceutical uses.

3.3. Future perspectives. Impact of using hypersaline media on the water footprint of microalgal cultivation

The water footprint measures the volume of freshwater removed from the environment by a given process and is a key tool in sustainability assessments (Guieysse et al., 2013). As microalgae cultivation is water-intensive, minimizing freshwater use is essential. Recent reviews addressed strategies such as water recycling and reuse (Farooq et al., 2015), yet none have considered the use of hypersaline culture media, based on reject brines from seawater desalination plants, in PBRs. This alternative could nearly eliminate freshwater demand in microalgae production systems, as discussed below. Freshwater use in PBRs arises from several sources: evaporation, blowdown for salinity control, periodic cleaning, biomass harvesting and drying, photosynthesis, the grey water footprint associated with pollutant dilution and system leakage (Farooq et al., 2015; Guieysse et al., 2013). Evaporation is the main source of freshwater loss in microalgal cultivation systems, particularly in open ponds. Reported evaporation rates, typically estimated using pan data, lake models or the Penman's equation, are based on freshwater cultures (Farooq et al., 2015; Guieysse et al., 2013), with limited data on marine or salt-tolerant species. However, increased salinity lowers the water activity, and thus the saturation vapour pressure, which reduces the latent heat flux of evaporation, leading to lower evaporation rates despite a slight rise in the surface water temperature (Mor et al., 2018). In fact, evaporation rate from a distilled water surface is twice as high as that from a saturated brine surface in open water bodies (Suchan and Azam, 2021). These differences were more pronounced during spring and summer.

In the culture system used in the present study, although the BC-PBRs were enclosed and covered, measurable cumulative differences in water loss among salinities were observed over the 80-day cultivation period. Total evaporative losses were approximately 1001 mL for CTRL-PBR, 920 mL for S50-PBR, and 899 mL for BRINE-PBR, representing 10 %, 9.2 %, and 9.0 % of the 10 L working volume, respectively, equivalent to daily evaporation rates of 1.3, 1.2, and 1.1 mL L⁻¹ day⁻¹. These values are consistent with theoretical evaporation rates under the operating conditions used (20 ± 1 °C, 1 L·min⁻¹ of compressed air at 6 bar and 0 % RH), assuming partial recondensation within the enclosed BC-PBR. However, for the measurement accuracy of culture variables, what matters most is not the cumulative loss but the temporary volume deviation between successive compensations. These intervals resulted in water losses ranging from ~160 mL to ~225 mL, corresponding to temporary variations of ~1.6 % to ~2.3 % of the working volume. This could cause a minor, temporary overestimation of biomass concentration if uncorrected. Nevertheless, evaporation was regularly compensated as discussed in section 2.4. While the absolute differences in evaporation between salinities were modest (~8–10 % lower at BRINE-PBR compared to CTRL-PBR), the trend supports the above hypothesis that increasing salinity reduces evaporative losses. These effects, although more pronounced in open systems, remain observable under closed-culture conditions and may contribute to improved water retention in long-term or large-scale operations with marine or halotolerant microalgae. Therefore, cultivating salt-tolerant microalgae in hypersaline media offers a promising strategy to reduce the water footprint and improving the sustainability of microalgal production in PBRs. Future efforts should focus on screening brackish and marine species that perform well across a wide range of salinities, particularly in hypersaline conditions, while maintaining or enhancing the production of target metabolites. Salt-adapted strains can also emerge from selective cultivation of freshwater species (Shetty et al., 2019). Furthermore, saline media can suppress contaminant organisms, providing a biological advantage (Bartley et al., 2013).

From a scale-up perspective, several challenges must be considered when using brine-based media in photobioreactors. While this study used bubble column photobioreactors, the findings are not limited to this PBR type. Indeed, different PBR configurations may be better suited

for scale-up depending on the final application. Light attenuation from longer optical paths and self-shading affects all dense cultures, and therefore would similarly affect other photobioreactor configurations. However, cultivating microalgae in hypersaline desalination brine introduces additional engineering and operational compared to freshwater or seawater-based systems. The high salt content (approx. 60 g L⁻¹) significantly increases the ionic strength of the culture medium, impairing gas-liquid mass transfer through the salting-out effect because the solubility of gases such as carbon dioxide is reduced as water molecules preferentially hydrate dissolved ions, limiting gas dissolution. Moreover, high ionic strength shifts the CO₂-bicarbonate-carbonate equilibrium, potentially reducing free CO₂ availability. This may hinder CO₂-dependent species but benefit those able to utilize bicarbonate via carbon-concentrating mechanisms. These findings underscore the need for tailored engineering solutions, such as enhanced mixing strategies, pressurized operation, or the use of gas-permeable membranes, to mitigate the limitations imposed by brine-based media. Future work should focus on quantifying these effects under varying salinity regimes.

Proximity to a sea or brackish water desalination plant would provide a steady, low-cost source of reject brine and saline water. Spent culture brines may be returned to the desalination plant for integration into its final brine disposal system. Zero liquid discharge strategies and recent advances in separation technologies enable recovery of valuable components from brine (Backer et al., 2022; Sharkh et al., 2022), in line with the "seawater hub" concept that promotes circular and sustainable desalination (Sajna et al., 2024). Despite these advancements, the current global volume of brine remains substantial, with only a negligible fraction currently recycled. Consequently, in coastal regions with a high density of desalination facilities, Environmental Impact Statements increasingly require compliance with salinity thresholds, necessitating brine dilution process prior to discharge into marine environments (Navarro-Barrio et al., 2021).

The study presented here is framed within the conceptual model for integrating seawater desalination with microalgal cultivation, as outlined in Fig. 2a and previously discussed. This framework aligns with an emerging strategy that warrants consideration, which focuses on the incorporation of effluents originated from hydroponic agriculture and desalination brine discharges as alternative nutrient sources for microalgal growth (López-Rosales et al., 2025). By embedding microalgal cultivation into existing industrial processes, these integrative approaches support the development of biorefineries based on closed-loop systems. Such systems leverage the synergy between waste valorisation and sustainable biomass production, thereby reducing resource demand, advancing circular economy principles, and contributing to zero-waste goals. Ultimately, this integration helps mitigate the environmental footprint associated with both waste generation and microalgal biomass production, which are central to the concept of sustainable biorefineries. While this study focused on high-value metabolites with greater biotechnological relevance—such as fatty acids, pigments, and bioactive extracts—a more comprehensive biochemical profiling, including proteins and carbohydrates, would complement these findings and strengthen future valorisation strategies.

4. Conclusions

Prymnesium parvum demonstrated strong growth across salinities from 5 to 61 g L⁻¹, including real seawater desalination brine, achieving biomass yields comparable to seawater controls. Fatty acid remodeling and carotenoid dynamics, particularly involving the diadinoxanthin cycle, indicate physiological acclimation. Bioassays revealed antimicrobial, antiproliferative, and antiphytopathogenic activities, supporting its potential in high-value bioproduct applications. These findings support its integration into brine-based biorefineries aligned with circular bioeconomy principles. Nevertheless, future studies should assess key limitations for industrial deployment, including long-term culture stability, risk of contamination, scalability constraints (e.g., CO₂ supply,

light attenuation), and overall economic feasibility under real-world conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

A. Contreras-Gómez: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **L. López-Rosales:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **J. Martínez Burgos:** Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Molina-Miras:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **M.C. Cerón-García:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **A. Sánchez-Mirón:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **F. García-Camacho:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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